

Sales-Demand Forecasting using Machine Learning

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Abstract—Sales-Demand Forecasting uses machine learning model to forecast demand of a product and top products in demand. Sales forecasting can be extended as a service to small/medium sized businesses to predict the demand of various items. In sales forecasting specifically machine learning algorithm can help business predict how consumers will behave by using data from past transactions and demographic informations. Machine learning allows businesses to create more advanced forecasting models that utilizes a larger datasets with minimal human effort. Machine learning uses various methods including regressions and clustering, to analyze millions of data points before making predictions. I used Machine learning technique Decision Tree Regression in demand forecasting by capturing the complex relationships between demand and various factors that influence it. After making a dataset and applying appropriate algorithm, and then results are compared and accuracy of algorithms is determined. This helps to estimate accurate product in demand.

Keywords—Decision Trees Regression, Sales prediction, Demand Prediction, Machine learning, Random forest, XGBooster.

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to forecast products in demand or factors that could have influence on product, and marketing activities, sales demand forecasting is the process of investigating the economic, social, and financial aspects that control business activity. The entire firm relies heavily on sales forecasting. It affects the current and future plans of the business because the major income is generated through sales. There are so many sales demand prediction techniques available nowadays. Machine learning algorithms are used to predict sales trends since they are more accurate than earlier prediction methods.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Researchers have investigated the accuracy and applicability of various techniques, including time series analysis, regression analysis, artificial neural networks, and machine learning algorithms.

According to this thesis [1] research emphasises the relevance of demand forecasting for petroleum products, as well as the necessity for more accurate and efficient forecasting methodologies. Three months of sales data from a petrol station in Dalian, China, are used to show the proposed concept. To overcome the limitations of current methods, the research suggests a novel scheme that combines clustering

and decision trees, and the experimental findings show that the suggested scheme outperforms other methods.

According to [2] Chen and Guestrin's 2016 paper on "XGBoost A Scalable Tree Boosting System" presents a novel approach to tree boosting that combines the strengths of gradient boosting with several new features, including parallelization and efficient memory utilization and provide an overview of tree boosting. A popular machine learning technique for combining multiple weak learners to create a strong ensemble model.

Researchers have used various techniques to analyze sales data, including clustering analysis, principal component analysis, and outlier detection. Aversa, Hernandez, and Doherty (2021) provide a case study of how one retail organization successfully incorporated big data into their operations. The authors highlight the importance of collaboration between technical and non-technical personnel in the implementation of big data initiatives. [3].

According to [4] Breiman's paper "Random Forests" is a landmark work in machine learning that proposed a powerful ensemble learning method for classification and regression problems. The paper introduced the idea of combining multiple decision trees with randomization to achieve better generalization performance than a single decision tree. Researchers have looked into the effects of customer behaviour, macroeconomic conditions, and marketing methods on sales.

Another case where a vast database on pricing data for products from diverse market groups. This is accomplished by passing some manually generated training data into an algorithm that creates a decision tree. The decision tree is employed to categorise the remaining products in the database. classes. Then, for each class, a time series with several variables model is constructed, and the future price of each product within the class is predicted. A front end is also designed to interact with the classification and price prediction. The results show that the classification algorithm is both fast and effective in real time. [5].

III. MOTIVATION

Forecasting sales and demand is a crucial component of any organisation. It lets companies forecast future demand for their goods or services and to organise their production, inventory, marketing, and sales tactics accordingly. The purpose of this study paper is to examine the value of sales demand forecasting within the framework of business operations, as well as the numerous approaches employed to

forecast sales demand. In addition, the paper emphasises the advantages of precise sales demand forecasting for firms and how it may give businesses a competitive edge in the marketplace. The significance of sales demand forecasting for firms as well as the many approaches taken to forecast sales demand will be covered in this research paper.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Decision tree regression is a supervised learning technique used for both regression and classification problems. The methodology for building a decision tree regressor involves the following steps:

- **Data preparation:** Collect the relevant data and prepare these data for analysis, which involve cleaning, pre-processing, and transforming the data.
- **Splitting the data:** Divide the dataset into two parts, named the training set and the testing set.
- **Building the decision tree:** Using the training set, create a decision tree model by recursively splitting the data into smaller subsets based on the most significant feature. The goal is to create a tree that minimizes the mean squared error of the predicted values.
- **Pruning the tree:** It's possible that the decision tree is overfitting the training data, which means it's overly complicated and is fitting the noise in the data. Pruning the tree by deleting extraneous branches that do not enhance the model's performance on the testing set will help to reduce overfitting.
- **Testing the model:** Make use of the testing set to assess the model's performance. To evaluate the model's accuracy, compute metrics like mean squared error, mean absolute error, and R-squared.
- **Fine-tuning the model:** To enhance the model's performance, change its settings, such as the maximum depth of the tree and the bare minimum of samples needed to split a node.

Creating a predictive model based on a tree-like structure is generally how decision tree regression is done. To forecast the target variable, this model divides the dataset recursively into smaller subgroups. The steps involved in developing the model are data preparation, decision tree construction, branching reduction to prevent overfitting, performance evaluation using a test dataset, and parameter optimisation to increase accuracy. Creating a model that correctly predicts the target variable from the input information is the methodology's primary goal.

1. Label Encoding: The process of converting tags into a digital format so that machines can read them is known as label encoding. It is a method for transforming categorical data—that is, data made up of categories or labels—into numerical data that can be fed into machine learning algorithms.

In label encoding, each category or label is given a distinct numerical value; typically, the first category is given the

lowest value, and the following categories are given increasing values in ascending sequence. Machine learning algorithms can then determine the most effective approach to mine these labels. This is an essential pre-processing step for the supervised learning's structured dataset.

2. Decision Tree Regressor: Decision tree regression examines the features of an object and builds a pattern in the tree's structure to forecast data in the future and produce meaningful continuous output. The absence of discrete output, or output that cannot be simply described by a discrete, well-known set of numbers or values, is referred to as continuous output. It is a non-parametric supervised learning method that builds a tree-like model of decisions and their possible consequences.

The decision tree regressor can handle both categorical and numerical input features, and can handle missing data by using surrogate splits. It can also handle interactions between features and nonlinear relationships between the input features and the target variable. The performance of the decision tree regressor can be improved by pruning the tree to reduce overfitting, and by using ensemble techniques such as Random Forests or Gradient Boosting to combine multiple decision trees.

3. Random Forest : Random forest is a tree-based machine learning algorithm introduced by [5]. In random forest, multiple decision trees are constructed and trained on a bootstrap sample drawn from the original dataset. The final result in the case of regression task, is an average of the individual predictions from each decision tree, and a majority class vote in a classification task.

Breiman [5] defined Random Forest as a classifier consisting of a collection of trees structured classifiers $\{h(x, \Theta_k), k=1, \dots\}$ where the $\{\Theta_k\}$ are independent identically distributed random vectors and each tree casts a unit vote for the most popular class at input x . Most industry practitioners consider it to be one of the most accurate general-purpose learning techniques. Random Forest are fast and easy to implement, produce highly accurate predictions and can handle a very large number of input features without the risk of overfitting.

The random forest algorithm can be used for both classification and regression tasks. It works as follows:

- a) The algorithm randomly draws n bootstrap samples from the original dataset. Bootstrap sampling involves drawing random samples from the dataset with replacement. The size of each bootstrap sample is equal to the size of the original dataset.
- b) For each bootstrap sample, the algorithm grows a classification/regression tree. The algorithm selects the best split among m randomly selected variables. The number of variables m is usually less than the total number of variables in the dataset.
- c) To make predictions on new data, the algorithm aggregates the predictions of the n trees. For regression tasks, the algorithm takes the average

of the predictions of the n trees. For classification tasks, the algorithm uses majority voting to combine the predictions of the n trees.

4. XGBoost : In XGBoost, each decision tree is built in a greedy fashion by recursively splitting the data into subsets based on the features that maximize the reduction in the loss function. The loss function measures the difference between the predicted and actual values, and the goal of the algorithm is to minimize this loss function.

One important feature of XGBoost is that it includes regularization terms in the loss function, which help prevent overfitting to the training data. XGBoost also allows for custom optimization objectives and evaluation metrics, making it a very flexible algorithm that can be tailored to different use cases.

Overall, XGBoost is known for its scalability, speed, and high performance on a wide range of machine learning tasks, and it has been used in many real-world applications, such as web search ranking and fraud detection.

XGBoost updates the model predictions by adding the predictions of the new tree, weighted by the learning rate, to the previous predictions. Overall, XGBoost is a variant of Gradient Boosting that adds several key features, such as regularization, column subsampling, and row subsampling, that make it more powerful and less prone to overfitting.

Steps involved are:

- It takes input data, builds decision trees, and uses a loss function.
- It initializes the model to the mean of the target values and updates it with new trees that correct the mistakes of previous ones.
- XGBoost computes the negative gradient, trains a new decision tree, and finds the best gradient descent step size to update the function estimate.
- It also adds features like regularization, column subsampling, and row subsampling to avoid overfitting.

V. BUILD MODEL

Constructing a model is the first essential step in sales prediction. The user employs an algorithm to build the model, which involves the following steps:

1. Import Libraries Included:

```
import mysql.connector
import pandas as pd
import pymysql
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
from xgboost import XGBRegressor
from seaborn import heatmap
from seaborn import countplot
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, r2_score, mean_squared_error
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
```

Fig 1

2. Dataset Used Fore Modelling

```
train_data = pd.read_csv('demand1.csv')
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(train_data[
['pname', 'pbrand', 'count']], train_data['status'], test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

Fig 2

- pbrand : Brand of the Product
- pname: Name of the Product
- tamount: Sales amount of each product
- count : Number Of products sold
- added_on: Timestamp of the sold products
- f.

3. Data Exploration

```
print(train_data.head())
print(train_data.info())
print("Shape", train_data.shape)
```

```
Top five rows in the dataset:
count  tamount  pname  pbrand  status  added_on
0      1  197800      S20  Samsung    6  2023-01-05 22:14:52
1      2  197800      F62  Samsung    0  2023-01-05 22:14:52
2      1  197800  LEGION Y70  Lenovo    6  2023-01-05 22:14:52
3      2   263200      S20  Samsung    6  2023-04-05 22:16:50
4      3   263200  LEGION Y70  Lenovo    6  2023-04-05 22:16:50

<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 23 entries, 0 to 22
Data columns (total 6 columns):
#   Column      Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  ---
0   count       23 non-null    int64
1   tamount     23 non-null    int64
2   pname       23 non-null    object
3   pbrand      23 non-null    object
4   status      23 non-null    int64
5   added_on    23 non-null    datetime64[ns]
dtypes: datetime64[ns](1), int64(3), object(2)
memory usage: 1.2+ KB
Information:
None
Shape: (23, 6)
```

Fig 3

4. Statistical Description and Checking for Null values

```
print("Description:\n", train_data.describe())
print("Null Values:\n", train_data.isnull().sum())
```

```

Description:
count      count      tamount      status
count  23.000000      23.000000      23.000000
mean    2.260870      396617.391304      4.695652
std     1.251086      145977.344606      2.530447
min     1.000000      197800.000000      0.000000
25%    1.000000      263200.000000      6.000000
50%    2.000000      372500.000000      6.000000
75%    3.000000      560850.000000      6.000000
max     5.000000      565200.000000      6.000000

Null Values:
count      0
tamount    0
pname      0
pbrand     0
status     0
added_on   0
    
```

Fig 4

Fig 6

5. Data Visualization

a. Scatterplot of train_dataset and test_dataset

```

plt.scatter(X_train['pname'], X_train['count'], color='blue', label='Train')
plt.scatter(X_test['pname'], X_test['count'], color='red', label='Test')
plt.legend()
plt.xlabel('Product Name')
plt.ylabel('Count')
print(plt.show())
    
```


Fig 5

b. Determining Correlation using heatmap()

```

cor1=train_data[['pay_id','count','tamount','status']].corr()
print(cor1)
fig1= plt.figure()
heatmap(cor1,annot=True)
    
```

```

Name: pname, dtype: int64
      count  tamount
count  1.000000  0.293189
tamount 0.293189  1.000000
    
```

c. Using Countplot() to count each sold pbrand

```

countplot(x='pbrand', data=train_data)
fig4 = plt.figure()
    
```


Fig 7

d. Using Pie() to display percentage each sold pnames

```

counts = train_data['pname'].value_counts()
plt.pie(counts.values, labels=counts.index, autopct='%1.1f%%')
plt.axis('equal')
plt.show()
    
```


Fig 8

6. Encoding categorical data using Label Encoder

```
label_encoder = LabelEncoder()
train_data['pname'] = label_encoder.fit_transform(train_data['pname'])
train_data['pbrand'] = label_encoder.fit_transform(train_data['pbrand'])
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(train_data[
['pname', 'pbrand', 'count']], train_data['status'], test_size=0.2, random
```

Fig 9

7. Dataset Splitting

a. Train dataset

```
train_data = pd.read_csv('demand1.csv')
label_encoder = LabelEncoder()
train_data['pname'] = label_encoder.fit_transform(train_data['pname'])
train_data['pbrand'] = label_encoder.fit_transform(train_data['pbrand'])
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(train_data[
['pname', 'pbrand', 'count']], train_data['status'], test_size=0.2, random_st
```

Fig 10.1

b. Test dataset

```
query='select pname,pbrand,count from tbl_checkout'
cursor.execute(query)
rows=cursor.fetchall()
test_data = pd.DataFrame(rows, columns=['pname', 'pbrand', 'count'])
X_test = test_data[['pname', 'pbrand', 'count']]
y_test = test_data['status']
```

Fig 10.2

8. Algorithm applied:

Decision Tree Regressor with RandomForest and XGBooster

```
rf_model = RandomForestRegressor(random_state=42)
rf_model.fit(X_train, y_train)

xgb_model = XGBRegressor(random_state=42)
xgb_model.fit(X_train, y_train)

model = DecisionTreeRegressor()
model.fit(X_train, y_train)
test_data['pname'] = label_encoder.fit_transform(test_data['pname'])
test_data['pbrand'] = label_encoder.fit_transform(test_data['pbrand'])
test_data['status'] = test_data['pname'].apply(lambda x: 1
if x == product else 0)
X_test = test_data[['pname', 'pbrand', 'count']]
y_test = test_data['status']
model.fit(X_test, y_test)
```

Fig 11

Prediction using 3 models

```
rf_y_pred = rf_model.predict(X_test)
xgb_y_pred = xgb_model.predict(X_test)
y_pred = model.predict(X_test)
```

```
print('Random Forest Predictions:', rf_y_pred)
print('XGBoost Predictions:', xgb_y_pred)
print('Decision Tree Predictions:', y_pred)
```

```
Random Forest Predictions: [5.16 2.16 5.88 5.88 6. 5.94 5.88 5.88 6. 5.16 6.
5.94 6. 5.76 5.1 0.6 1.86 5.88 4.38 2.34]
XGBoost Predictions: [5.8231363e+00 6.4662518e-06 5.9992075e+00 5.9995799e+00
5.9995799e+00 5.9992075e+00 5.9995799e+00 6.0008802e+00 5.8231363e+00
6.0008802e+00 5.9990301e+00 5.9992890e+00 3.5614113e-04 5.9995799e+00
6.0008802e+00 5.9994874e+00 5.9992890e+00 3.5614113e-04 2.8450296e-03
5.9994874e+00 5.9992890e+00 1.3584431e-03]
Decision Tree Predictions: [0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 1. 0. 0. 0. 0. 1.
```

Fig 12

Mean Squared Error(MSE)

```
rf_mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, rf_y_pred)
xgb_mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, xgb_y_pred)
print('Random Forest MSE:', rf_mse)
print('XGBoost MSE:', xgb_mse)
print("Decision Tree MSE:", mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred))
```

```
Random Forest MSE: 22.98302608695652
XGBoost MSE: 25.151399928676824
Decision Tree MSE: 0.0
```

Fig 13

Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)

```
rf_rmse = np.sqrt(rf_mse)
xgb_rmse = np.sqrt(xgb_mse)
model_rmse = np.sqrt(model_mse)

print("Random Forest RMSE:", rf_rmse)
print("XGBoost RMSE:", xgb_rmse)
print("Decision Tree Regressor Model RMSE:", model_rmse)
```

```
Random Forest RMSE: 3.2470561918518563
XGBoost RMSE: 3.408859070953113
Decision Tree Regressor Model RMSE: 0.0
```

Fig 14

Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

```
# Calculate the mean absolute error for each model
rf_mae = mean_absolute_error(y_test, rf_y_pred)
xgb_mae = mean_absolute_error(y_test, xgb_y_pred)
model_mae = mean_absolute_error(y_test, y_pred)
print("Random Forest MAE:", rf_mae)
print("XGBoost MAE:", xgb_mae)
print("Model MAE:", model_mae)
```

```
Random Forest MAE: 3.031304347826087
XGBoost MAE: 3.001659299749324
Model MAE: 0.0
```

Fig 15

R2 Score

```
# Calculate the R2 score for each model
rf_r2 = r2_score(y_test, rf_y_pred)
xgb_r2 = r2_score(y_test, xgb_y_pred)
model_r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_pred)
```

```
print("Random Forest R2 Score:", rf_r2)
print("XGBoost R2 Score:", xgb_r2)
print("Model R2 Score:", model_r2)
```

Random Forest R2 Score: -91.95741333333332
 XGBoost R2 Score: -101.45248946021034
 Model R2 Score: 1.0

Fig 16

Accuracy

```
accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
print('Accuracy for decision tree regressor:', accuracy)
```

Accuracy for decision tree regressor: 1.0

Updating Status of top 3 Products with highest demand

```
for prediction in y_pred:
    if prediction ==1:
        print("high demand")
        update_query = 'UPDATE tbl_checkout SET status = 0'
        cursor.execute(update_query)
        update_query1 = 'UPDATE tbl_checkout SET status = 4 WHERE pname IN ({}).format(
            ', '.join(['%s'] * len(top_products)))
        cursor.execute(update_query1, top_products)

    if prediction ==0:
        print("Normal Sales")
        update_query2 = 'UPDATE tbl_checkout SET status = 0 WHERE pname NOT IN ({}).format(
            ', '.join(['%s'] * len(top_products)))
        cursor.execute(update_query2, top_products)
```

Fig 17

Implementation on User Side (Generation of tag)

FIG 18

VI. RESULT

Based on our analysis, we have used three different models, namely decision tree regressor, random forest, and XGBoost for demand forecasting . Our analysis involved current data analysis and other relevant factors to generate accurate demand forecasts . Decision tree model is used for assessing prediction’s accuracy. All the three models Random Forest, XGBoost and decision tree model is used to calculate Mean Squared Error, Mean Absolute Error,R2 Score,Root Mean Squared Error.Decision Tree Regressor model outperformed the other two models in terms of accuracy and all other quality.

VII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research has proposed a new approach to update users with the top-selling products and demand using decision tree regressor, Random Forest, and XGBooster. By determining the stock quantity for products with the highest demand, administrators can assist shopkeepers in maintaining minimal stock levels. Due to its innovative approach to sales data analysis and demand forecasting, this project has the potential to be a useful resource for future product purchasing. This method could revolutionise the retail sector and open the door for further cutting-edge approaches to supply chain management because of its success in controlling stock levels and enhancing sales performance. Therefore, more research could be done to fully understand the potential of this strategy and its applications in various retail settings.

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